

TOWARDS UNDERSTANDING AND MODELING IRREVERSIBLE BEHAVIOR OF WOVEN FABRICS UNDER LOADING-UNLOADING BENDING REGIMES

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Introduction

Woven fabric composites are among widely utilized materials in modern industrial products. These composites have been increasingly used in primary structural components of aircrafts such as Boeing 777, Boeing 787, and Airbus A350. There are several key aspects that should be considered during the manufacturing (forming) process of woven composites. Friction between and within fiber tows/yarns, fiber twist and fiber misalignment can lead to a large variability and non-repeatability of forming outcome [1, 2]. In turn, these key factors can result in a non-reversible behavior of the reinforcing fabric during loading-unloading conditions, e.g. those of inflatable woven structures. A meso-level numerical analysis is adopted to assess the effect of friction, angle of rotation, and material parameters on the irreversible bending behavior of a typical woven fabric under a full loading-unloading cycle.

Figure 1 The custom bending device to measure the varying bending stiffness. Force - curvature of Twintex fabric through a loading-unloading cycle.

Experiment and Finite Element Modelling: Bending Tests

The bending behavior of a dry thermoplastic woven fabric is investigated using a new custom test set-up (Figure 1). Once the gripper is fixed and the fabric undergoes pure bending, the load cell reads the reaction force due to the movement of the circular movement of the other gripper. The distance between the grippers is fixed at 1cm.

A meso-level FE model of the above bending test is established in Abaqus (Figure 2), where the yarns geometry was modelled directly via Python scripting using a sinusoidal function presented in [3]. An iterative inverse method is utilized to achieve optimum parameters of the hyper-elastic and Mullin effect [4].

Figure 2 Micro-CT scan of Twintex and the finite element model

Results

In the parameter identification process, the maximum force during loading-unloading regime, and the nonlinear response during unloading were compared iteratively with the simulation until a good agreement was found. The contact friction coefficient at crossovers was tested separately and was found to be 0.35.

An appropriate yarn material model for the current application needed to consider (i) the nonlinear mechanical behavior during loading and (ii) the energy 'loss' during unloading regime. The Mullin effect model is deemed capable of meeting these key aspects. The model was compared with the experiments. The results showed that the FE model is able to capture the dissipation of energy through the loading-unloading regime accurately.

Figure 3 Comparison of experiments and simulations

Sensitivity Analysis

We study the effect of friction coefficient (μ) and angle of rotation (θ ; in radians) as well as the yarn material bending on the resulting nonlinear bending behavior of a unit cell of the fabric as well as the effect of two layers on the cyclic loading. A Python script was written to automatically run 24 combinations of friction and angle of rotation (Table 1). Also, irreversible bending behavior of a single and two-layer woven fabric is investigated.

Figure 4 Representative Unit Cells

Figure 5 Comparison of one and two layer and the variance of effective parameters (friction, curvature, yarn material) on the bending behavior of fabrics under cyclic loading

Conclusion

Due to the presence of fiber twist, geometrical non-linearities, crimp and undulation, and dominant friction and shearing between filaments within yarns and between yarns at cross overs, the irreversible behavior of the fabrics during forming regimes are likely. In this work a numerical model was employed at the meso-level to investigate anti-plane deformation of a typical dry thermoplastic woven fabric under a loading-unloading bending cycle.

The analysis showed that

- The effects of curvature and yarn material rigidity are significant.
- Further study showed that the frictional interaction at crossovers yields to approximately 5% of the relative energy dissipation through one load cycle based on the moment-curvature curves.
- The yarn material rigidity for any given curvature was found to be significant statistically, while all other interaction parameters were insignificant.
- The moment-curvature curves of a single and two-layer made of four unit cells shows the nonlinear variation of bending rigidity of two-layer is approximately two times the bending rigidity of the one-layer.

Table 1. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the effect of parameters under cyclic bending of the representative unit cell.

Factors	DOF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F	P-Value
Friction	2	0.23	0.11	0.55	0.6035
Bending Angle	3	198.85	66.28	331.40	4.7115e-7
(Yarn) Material	1	1.52	1.52	7.60	0.03299
Friction× Bending Angle	6	1.20	0.20	1.0	0.5
Friction× Material	2	0.21	0.11	0.55	0.6035
Bending Angle× Material	3	1.03	0.34	1.70	0.2654
Error	6	1.17	0.20		
Total	23	204.21			

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